

Teaching Pedagogical Accompaniment In Virtual Education During The Pandemic

By

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Abstract

Teacher accompaniment in virtual education implies that RBE teachers implement strategies for developing meaningful learning in students, all taking into account the health guidelines on social isolation and the “I learn at home” strategy. Experiences regarding successful teaching in virtual education are shared, where the use of the strategy “I learn at home” has tools, resources and materials that teachers can use, students and family members at home; in the same way, it proposes the development of activities, allowing students from different parts of the country, to participate through radio, television and internet. Because of this, there is an urgent need for teachers to pertinently review the resources according to the needs, follow-up and evaluation; therefore, the directors and specialists of the Ugel carry out the pedagogical accompaniment of teachers according to their pedagogical practice for the optimization of student learning and the improvement of educational quality at the district, regional and national level.

Thus, after more than a year of the presence of the pandemic, and taking into account the learning ocre of the year 2020 and so far in 2021, it can be said that changes in curricular programs are urgently needed to increase knowledge, skills development, activities, changes in methodology, research techniques, as well as the proper use of resources and materials that are proposed, to meet the interests, needs and limitations of students.

Keywords: pedagogical support, virtual education, cognitive and didactic processes, pandemic.

Resumen

El acompañamiento docente en la enseñanza virtual, implica que los docentes de EBR, implementen estrategias para el desarrollo de aprendizaje significativos en los estudiantes; todo teniendo en cuenta los lineamientos sanitarios en el aislamiento social y la estrategia Aprendo en casa. Se comparte las experiencias referentes a la enseñanza con éxito en la educación virtual; donde la utilización de la estrategia “Aprendo en casa”, cuenta con herramientas, recursos y materiales que pueden utilizar los docentes, estudiantes y los familiares en los

hogares; de la misma manera, propone el desarrollo de actividades, permitiendo que los estudiantes de los diferentes lugares del país, participen a través del radio, televisión e internet. Ante ello, urge la necesidad de que los docentes revisen pertinentemente los recursos de acuerdo a las necesidades, seguimiento y evaluación; por ello, los directivos y especialistas de la Ugel realicen el acompañamiento pedagógico docente de acuerdo a su práctica pedagógica para la optimización de los aprendizajes en el estudiante y la mejora de la calidad educativa a nivel distrital, regional y nacional. Así, luego de más de un año de la presencia de la pandemia, y teniendo en cuenta el ogro de los aprendizaje del año 2020 y lo que va del 2021, se puede afirmar que urge los cambios en las programaciones curriculares tendientes al incremento de conocimientos, desarrollo de habilidades, actividades, cambios en la metodología, técnicas de investigación, así como la utilización adecuada de recursos y materiales que se proponen, para la atención de intereses, necesidades y limitaciones de los estudiantes.

Palabras clave: acompañamiento pedagógico, educación virtual, procesos cognitivos y didácticos, pandemia.

Introduction

A major challenge facing educational systems as educational institutions close is not a guarantee that they will continue to achieve student learning, such as the significant shift from the face-to-face model to remote learning. Currently, there are still many critics about the immediate return of face-to-face classes, which guarantees equality, and that all students have access to education; therefore, the role of managers for the reorganization of the educational institution, teamwork with teachers, non-teachers, students and community (Castro, 2020).

Social isolation, in the national contingency and adjusting the institutional directives and the continuation of quality educational service, with a new educational model, methodological strategies that were implemented in virtual classrooms, with a role of the teacher and continuous and essential accompaniment; therefore, the contingency plan was arranged as a straitjacket, but as the possibility of meeting and comprehensive accompaniment. The meetings and counseling spaces allowed all students to share their doubts and concerns during the development of learning activities (Valencia, 2020).

The pedagogical accompaniment is like a meeting generated in space through dialogue, empathy and active listening, promoting the transmission of knowledge and the generation of knowledge while allowing the student to interact with the teacher (Novoa and Pirella, 2020).

Thus, distance pedagogical accompaniment arises, which accompanies and strengthens the development of competencies in the teachers of educational institutions and progressively assumes their role as mediator with students during remote teaching, with personalized advice for pedagogical guidance for the achievement of learning, accompanying and supporting students, promoting communication and interaction with the family, and collaborative work among teachers (Ministry of Education, 2020).

In the same sense, it was pointed out that education must respond to the demands and

requirements of society in order to guarantee a quality education that will lead to the formation of competent people who can adapt to changes and solve challenges that arise in their social environment. Therefore, it is observed in Peru and worldwide that there is difficulty on the part of managers in educational institutions to accompany their teachers to improve their performance in remote teaching. Therefore, it was stated that the expert performance of instructors is focused on the continuous improvement of learning approaches, which are generated through timely and consistent activities developed by students (Vega and Vasquez, 2021).

Development

In 2015, the implementation of pilots began in Peru, which meant increasing hours and accompanying students through a tutoring and pedagogical reinforcement role, providing tools to teachers to develop learning activities, achieve training on the use of technological tools and optimize teaching performance.

This is where the action of accompanying in a planned, continuous, contextualized, interactive and respectful way new knowledge acquired by each teacher, manager and other person involved in order to immediately improve the quality levels of student learning, teaching practice and the way an educational institution is managed, which results in better management of educational quality (Yana and Adco, 2018)

The Ministry of Education stated that pedagogical accompaniment is the planning of actions, which are permanent, systematic and comprehensive, that are directed to teachers for the detection of errors, the application of some corrective through counseling, consultations, indications or explanations, which conform to the criteria of a good human relationship, which implies a change in teachers (Minedu, 2015).

It is necessary that teacher training is combined with accompaniment that improves teaching practice in the classroom, strengthening the complementary disciplinary knowledge of teaching practice; this is a training challenge for teachers, where accompaniment is necessary and important.

The accompanist must guide the teacher to provide feedback on their work to improve day by day, provide learning tools according to their needs, and connect them with other teachers of the same level, subject and context, share their current pedagogical practice and learn together (Monteza, 2020).

Most government responses are focused on establishing challenges in the availability and management of technological tools, challenges due to the lack of parental support for their children to learn at home, as well as the inability and unwillingness of teachers to apply the adaptation to change generated by the pandemic situation (OECD, 2020)

Each government attends each principle of virtual teaching in facing the pandemic through the development of activities that are mediated but technology, with the use of some device, connectivity and alternative study space in the continuity of classes, implementing the

technological resource based on experience, preparation and difficulty; to the evaluation and support that is received, adapting and projecting learning, with the prevalent use of laptop and smartphone, for the study, as well as sending and receiving information.

There the accompaniment to teachers is generated, enabling training, virtual platforms, and software, which represent important activities to continue with the studies (Portillo et al., 2020).

Also, the difference between the types of instruction that are carried out in normal conditions and another that is carried out in difficult circumstances, such as time, delay, as well as the minimum use of resources for the completion of tasks, as well as the conditions at the end of the tasks, going from the experience of a classroom training to another at a distance with a digital platform, which is a consequence of social isolation, and brings with it, inequity, generating large differences between age groups in society (Hodges et al., 2020).

In the same way, the scenario in the different educational institutions was transformed, moving the teaching-learning process to a virtual scenario, which forced the educational institutions to develop activities for the change towards remote teaching, where web 2.0 became the instrument that facilitated this transition, generating changes in the place and the way learning activities are developed, with a new role, both for the teacher and the student (Salas, 2020).

The pandemic generated by Covid-19 induced many teachers to conduct self-taught classes, which were then implemented with training provided to teachers, who learned to use technological tools and virtual environments, obtaining different results, where the classic distance education, with the existing means of communication, differed from remote teaching, which used videoconferencing, trying to imitate face-to-face classes, and also, each teacher had to develop their educational material (Marotias, 2020).

Methodology

The research follows a qualitative approach of a systematic review and is based on the adaptation of the PRISMA method, which according to Gómez (2012), begins with the process of searching for information, organizing it, and an analysis of the information collected; and Vera (2009), who pointed out the thorough review, with the description and evaluation of the selected articles, using keywords; and for the research accompanied in remote teaching, 94 documents were found in indexed journals related to educational research such as Scopus, Ebsco and Scielo.

The unit of analysis or sample was articles found in the Scopus, Ebsco and Scielo databases, and the search criteria were keywords: accompaniment, pedagogical accompaniment, and remote teaching. Also, the information was selected according to the objective, taking into account: the title, author(s), abstract and results; where Vera (2009) pointed out that it is to take into account the relevance of the title, credibility of the authors, the correctness of the abstract and whether the results can be used in the topic of study.

In the same way, 42 articles were pre-selected. Then, after an exhaustive analysis, 15 articles were chosen in the recovery of the information; according to Gómez (2012), the information collected was consulted and selected that which is useful for the study to be carried out; although the information collected is important for the study, it was not recovered; however, some documents were used; and scientific documents were taken from Scopus, Ebsco and Scileo; and all the cited sources were referenced.

Fifteen articles related to the unit of analysis which is teachers, were considered, and articles that referred to students and other units of analysis were excluded; in the same way, articles between the years 2017 and 2020 were considered; and years prior to 2016 were excluded.

Results And Discussion

Figure 1. Adapted from PRISMA Flow Diagram

Table 1 Research included in the systematic review

No.	Authors/ Year/ Title/ Publisher	Remote teaching support			Methodology	
		Accompaniment	Pedagogical support	Teaching remote	Type of study	Instrument, technique or method
1	Gerbaldo, G; Granato, P. (2020). <i>Accompaniment in times of pandemic: an invitation to reflection?</i> National University of Córdoba. Faculty of Philosophy and Humanities; 2020; 161-165.	X			Qualitative	Case study
	Gómez, A. (2012). <i>The documentary compilation. For what and how to document in documentary information sciences.</i> University of Murcia.	X			Qualitative	Case study
	Hodges, C., Moore, S., Lockee, B., Trust, T., & Bond, A. (2020). The difference between emergency remote teaching and online learning. Educause. Retrieved from https://er.educause.edu/articles/2020/3/the-difference-between-emergency-remoteteaching-and-online-learning			X	Qualitative	Case Study
	Ministry of Education (2015). <i>Working guidelines for the Pedagogical Coordinator.</i> Jornada Escolar Completa Secundaria, Lima-Peru.		X		Qualitative	Case Study
5	Monteza, G. (2020). Accompanying teachers in times of pandemic. <i>Education Journal. Informed dialogue on public policies.</i>		X		Qualitative	Interview
	Novoa, A., & Pirela, J. (2020). Accompaniment from an ethics of life : To educate in times of pandemic. <i>International Journal of Philosophy and Social Theory</i> , 25, 11-24.					

https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3931040 . https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3931040	X		Qualitative Documentary review
Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2020). <i>A framework to guide an education response to the COVID-19 pandemic of 2020</i> https://www.hm.ee/sites/default/files/framework_guide_v1_002_harward.pdf		X	Qualitative Documentary review
Picón, G.; Gonzáles, G. and Paredes, J. (2020). Performance and educational training in digital competences in nonpresential classes during the COVID-19 pandemic. Performance and educational training in digital competences in nonpresential classes during the covid-19 pandemic. <i>Scientific and Technological Research</i> . María Serrana Private University, Asunción, Paraguay.	X	X	Quantitative Questionnaire
Portillo, S., Castellanos, L., Reynoso, O., & Gavotto, O. (2020). Emergency remote teaching in the face of the Covid-19 pandemic in Middle and Higher Education. <i>Purposes and Representations</i> , 8 (SPE3), e589. Doi: http://dx.doi.org/10.20511/pyr2020.v8nSPE3.589	X	X	Qualitative Case Study
Valencia, W. (2020). A look at educational and pedagogical practices in times of pandemic. <i>REDPPI. Network of Pedagogical Research Practices</i> .	X		Qualitative Documentary review
Vega, P. and Vásquez, C. (2021). Pedagogical accompaniment and teaching performance in primary education. Pedagogical accompaniment and teaching performance in primary education. <i>Revista Espacios</i> . Vol. 42 (19) 2021. Art. 1	X	X	Quantitative Questionnaire
Vera, O. (2009). How to write review articles. <i>Revista Médica La Paz</i> v.15 n.º La Paz. Yana, M. and Adco, E. (2018). Pedagogical support and the teaching role in full school day: Case of educational institutions Santa Rosa and Salesianos of San Juan Bosco - Puno Peru. Pedagogical support and the teaching role in full school day: Case of			

educational institutions Santa Rosa and Salesianos of San Juan Bosco - Puno Perú. <i>Altoandina research journal</i> . vol.20 no.1 Puno Jan./Mar. 2018.	X	Quantitative	Questionnaire
Salas, D. A. (2020). Remote teaching and social networks: strategies and challenges for shaping learning communities. <i>Revista Andina De Educación</i> , 4(1), 36-42. https://doi.org/10.32719/26312816.2021.4.1.5 . https://doi.org/10.32719/26312816.2021.4.1.5 .	X	Quantitative	Questionnaire
Marotias, A. (2020). Emergency remote education and the dangers of imitating the face-to-face <i>Revista Hipertextos</i> , 8 (14), pp. 173-177. DOI: https://doi.org/10.24215/23143924e025	X	Qualitative	Documentary review
Lederman, D. (2020). Will shift to remote teaching be boon or bane for online learning? <i>Inside Higher</i> . https://www.insidehighered.com/digitallearning/article/2020/03/18/most-teaching-going-remote-will-help-or-hurt-onlinelearning	X	Qualitative	Documentary review

The table results allowed to distribute the information search results, with 50.0% related to the remote teaching subcategory, where three were able to interrelate with the other subcategories. 37.5% responds to the category pedagogical accompaniment related to other subcategories. Finally, 12.5% corresponds to the accompaniment subcategory. Of the research collected, 62.5% was qualitative in approach, while 37.5% was quantitative.

After analyzing the results, it was determined that pedagogical accompaniment and remote teaching were the subcategories that prevailed in the study of pedagogical accompaniment in remote teaching; a discussion was held that responded to the research objectives.

For pedagogical support in virtual teaching in times of pandemic, it can be stated that, according to the information reviewed, the strategy was used in conjunction with the State and private companies regarding the use of the internet and mobile telephony for both students and teachers to have free access to learning platforms.

Thus, it can be affirmed in the review of the information that, according to Portillo et al. (2020), managed to address the educational crisis with the presence of the pandemic, with remote teaching accompanied by technological tools and virtual environments in work in and with students; using mobile devices,

such as cell phones, laptop; a free connectivity at certain times for the strategy I learn at home; where teachers used their skills and abilities to adapt the curriculum, innovating strategies; it is there where the teacher accompaniment begins, enabling virtual training, virtual technological tools, which were used to perform their teaching function and continue with the students' studies.

In the same way, it is similar to the study of Vega and Vásquez (2021), who refers to an education that guarantees the demands and needs of quality education to form competent citizens, who can face challenges and changes, and can solve daily problems, thus, both in Peru and in the world, there are difficulties on the part of the directors of the educational institutions, and a good teaching accompaniment is carried out so that the improvement of remote teaching is achieved. Given this, it can be affirmed that the accompaniment of expert instructors focuses on improving learning approaches, which is generated through the use of appropriate and consistent strategies to be developed with students.

Also, regarding the pedagogical accompaniment, Minedu (2020) manages to accompany and strengthens the development of the competence of teachers in all educational institutions, as the classroom scenario moved to homes, where the teacher manages to assume his role as mediator in the learning of students during remote teaching, performs his role in a personalized way, guiding the student in the pedagogical, social and affective aspects, providing comprehensive support, involving the family in the student's learning; Novoa and Pirella (2020) also pointed out that the space where there is a meeting between the pedagogical instructor and the teacher, carried out with empathy and permanent listening, where new knowledge is transmitted. Knowledge is generated, for a suitable interaction between the teacher and the student.

In the same sense, as pointed out by Monteza (2020), with a need for ongoing support to teachers to improve their teaching practice in virtual classrooms to strengthen their knowledge in the computer aspect with the use of technological tools, as well as the development of materials according to the strategy used; they can share virtually with other teachers in their area, in the search for better learning in students. Likewise, also, was pointed out by the OECD (2020), where the governments of all countries implement in the teachers' strategies for the use of new technological tools, being this a challenge for teachers the application the strategy I learn at home, looking for the participation of the parents due to the abrupt change in the educational methodology that was generated by the pandemic situation.

In the same way, the research analyzed allowed to relate to the study of Salas (2020), which points out the obligation of educational institutions to change the methodology from presence to distance methodology, i.e., the change of remote teaching through the web 2.0 platform, which was able to facilitate these changes, generating the change of spaces from the classroom to the home, where the teacher assumed his mediating role; and at the same time the study of Marotías (2020) who described the new attitude of the teacher in the change of methodology, who started it in a self-taught way, and who was later trained in the use of virtual environments. However, this did not determine the same results as in the classroom, differing from remote teaching, videoconferencing, and trying to mimic the classroom spaces as much as possible.

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